

THE BRIGHT STAR OF UZBEK POETRY: THE LIFE AND WORK OF MUHAMMAD YUSUF

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Abstract: This article analyzes the life and creative activity of Muhammad Yusuf, his place in Uzbek literature, and the artistic features of his poetry. The poet's works highlight love for the Motherland, the pain of the people, national values, and the expression of human emotions. It also discusses the importance of Muhammad Yusuf's works in the development of Uzbek poetry and his popular poems that have found a place in the hearts of the people. The article aims to demonstrate the importance of studying the poet's literary heritage and passing it on to the younger generation.

Keywords: Muhammad Yusuf, Uzbek poetry, poet's works, theme of the Motherland, national values, Uzbek literature, artistic creativity, poetry.

Introduction. There are some poets whose poems live not on the pages of books, but in the hearts of the people. One of such creators is the Uzbek poet Muhammad Yusuf, who has gained a place in the hearts of millions of people with his simple, sincere, and heartfelt lines. His poems stand out for their deep expression of love for the Motherland, the pain of the people, and human emotions.

Muhammad Yusuf was born on April 26, 1954, in the Marhamat district of the Andijan region, in a simple peasant family. Since his childhood passed in a rural environment, he knew the life, traditions, and lifestyle of the people very

well. This environment later had a great influence on the appearance of sincere and realistic images in his poems.

After finishing school, due to his interest in literature, he came to Tashkent to continue his studies. Muhammad Yusuf studied at one of the higher educational institutions in Tashkent, at the Institute of Russian Language and Literature (now Uzbekistan State World Languages University), and began to seriously engage in literature and creative writing. Even during his student years, his first poems began to be published in newspapers and magazines. This strengthened the young poet's confidence in his work.

Poem Dedicated to Andijan

Why should I not bow to Andijan,

I was born here, I grew up here.

If I have one friend, that friend is here –

Why should I not bow to Andijan!

May my memory burn if I forget,

Let the Dukchi Eshons cry out.

Those like Mashrab who circled it,

Why should I not bow to Andijan!

After completing his studies, he worked in various places, including the Republic Society of Book Lovers, and later in newspapers and publishing houses. His work in the newspaper “Tashkent Evening” played an important role in his creative development. There, he became acquainted with famous writers and poets of that time.

His poems began to appear frequently in newspapers and magazines such as “Sharq Yulduzi” and “Guliston.” His simple language, sincerity, and unique love for the Motherland distinguished him from other poets. The main themes of his works are love for the Motherland, loyalty to the homeland, the life of the people, humanity, and sincere feelings. Many of his poems became very popular among the people. Some were even turned into songs and spread widely.

Therefore, Muhammad Yusuf is often recognized as a “people’s poet.”

He began his creative activity in the 1970s. His first poems were published in 1976 in the newspaper “Literature and Art of Uzbekistan.” From that time, he became known as a talented and popular poet.

From 1978 to 1980, he worked at the Society of Book Lovers. From 1980 to 1986, he worked at the “Tashkent Evening” newspaper. From 1986 to 1992, he worked at the Gafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art. He also worked at the “Voice of Uzbekistan” newspaper and other information organizations. First Poetry Book. The poet’s first poetry collection, titled “Familiar Poplars,” was published in 1985. This book reflects the initial stage of the young poet’s work and includes poems mainly about rural life, childhood memories, natural landscapes, and human feelings. Through this collection, Muhammad Yusuf began to be recognized as a new voice in Uzbek poetry. The book attracted readers with its simple, folk-like, and sincere style.

Example from the collection

My familiar poplars, I have come again,
I remembered my childhood paths again.

Your leaves whisper in the wind,
As if still waiting for me.

This poem expresses childhood memories and longing for the native village.

Lines About the Motherland

My heart beats every moment for my homeland,
Where you are, there is my happiness.
A piece of your soil is dearer than gold,
With you my life is spring and blossom.

Lines About Nature

At dawn I go out to the fields,
The sun smiles in the dew.
With a new dream in my heart,

My homeland calls me again.

Muhammad Yusuf's poem "Tulip" is considered one of the most emotional and famous works not only in his творчество but in all Uzbek poetry. This poem was dedicated to his close friend, the talented poet Shavkat Rahmon. Shavkat Rahmon was known for his strong character and rebellious poetry. When he became seriously ill, Muhammad Yusuf was deeply affected by his condition.

After his friend's death, when the poet visited his grave in spring, he saw red tulips blooming around it. This scene inspired him to write the poem, comparing his friend's life to a tulip — beautiful but short-lived

Tulip, tulip,
Red tulip like a wounded heart,
You remained asleep in the mountains,
Crying out against the stones...

In this poem, the tulip symbolizes the poet's friend, its red color represents deep emotion and pain, and its short life reflects the brevity of human life.

Muhammad Yusuf highly valued family life. His wife, Nazira as-Salom, supported him throughout his life. Themes such as love, loyalty, and sincerity are reflected in his poetry. For example: "Your smile is my peace, the warmest light in my heart." Awards Muhammad Yusuf received many awards and titles. In 1998, he was awarded the title "People's Poet of Uzbekistan." This title confirms his important place in Uzbek literature and his popularity among the people.

- Events Dedicated to Him
- Literary evenings and memorial events
- Scientific conferences
- Book publications and reprints
- Memorial events organized by his family

Muhammad Yusuf died on July 29, 2001. His death was a great loss for Uzbek literature. He was a poet who had gained a place in the hearts of the people with his sincere poems.

After his death, his literary heritage was widely recognized. His wife Nazira as-Salom and his children worked to preserve his memory and pass his works on to the younger generation.

References

1. Muhammad Yusuf. “Familiar Poplars” — Tashkent, 1985
2. Muhammad Yusuf. “Supplication” — Tashkent, 1988
3. Muhammad Yusuf. “Sleeping Girl” — Tashkent, 1989
4. Muhammad Yusuf. “Selected Works” — Tashkent, 2019
5. Muhammad Yusuf. “Poet’s Love” — Tashkent, 2016
6. Nazira as-Salom. “I Miss You, Muhammad Yusuf” — 2012
7. S. Sayyid. “Muhammad Yusuf in the Memory of Contemporaries” — 2004